

SUBJECTIVE OBSERVATION OF PATIENTS: IDENTIFICATION OF THE MAIN CAUSES OF HYPERPROLACTINEMIA IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7902310>

Annotation: Currently, an increase in the amount of prolactin is observed mainly in girls in puberty. Therefore, a subjective observation was made among girls aged 16 to 25 years. And as a result, it was found that 0,9 of the main cause of increased prolactin is hypothyroidism, and 0,1 are tumors and malignant tumors of the pituitary gland.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, pituitary gland, thyroid gland, prolactin, swelling, vitamin D general, prolactin, MRI of the brain.

Actually: Hyperprolactinemia (HPrl) is considered as a rare endocrinopathy in childhood. In children and adolescent girls, there are three major categories of HPrl causes; physiological, pathological and iatrogenic.

Through hypogonadotropic hypogonadism, prolactin hypersecretion and production leads to the typical functional syndrome which is observed in female children and adolescents; delayed puberty, primary or secondary amenorrhea and/or galactorrhea. Regarding prolactinomas, clinical signs manifest with mass compression of the optic chiasm and anterior pituitary gland or prolactin hypersecretion. Targeted identification of HPrl is of significant importance for proper management and follow-up. The aim of this review is to focus on the evaluation of HPrl in adolescent and young girls.

Introduction: Hyperprolactinemia (HPrl) with a prevalence of 0.4% to 5% is considered a frequent endocrinopathy, although rare in childhood. Prolactin is one of the major pituitary hormones that is secreted from the pituitary gland and plays an important role in reproductive functions. The normal serum prolactin concentration level in female children and adolescents is between 5 and 20 ng/ml [1, 2]. Prolactin is produced from the lactotropic cells of the anterior pituitary lobe in response to a singular and unique tonic inhibitory (dopamine) signal that is prevalent on the stimulatory TRH (thyrotropin-releasing hormone) hormonal signals [3]. The elevated prolactin levels in interruption of peduncle or in obstruction of portal venous system is due to loss of inhibitory action of dopamine. Several agents such as stress, suckling, estrogens, TRH, vasoactive intestinal polypeptide (VIP) and oxytocin, among others, act as stimulants of prolactin release directly to anterior lobe or by

reducing the in-hibitory action of dopamine. The primary activity of prolactin is its lactotrophic effect on the epithelium of the mammary gland as well as regulating gonadal function by inhibiting GnRH excretion and secretion of Follicle stimulation hormone (FSH) and Luteinizing hormone(LH) . Interestingly, prolactin also demonstrates regulatory effects in the immune system, lactation, adipose tissue and insulin secretion. The clinical manifestations of HPrl are various but usually specific and easy to recognize only in ado-lescence, while in childhood onset symptomatology is neurologic with headache and visual deficit. Once the presence of prolactin hypersecretion is identified, further evaluation to establish the underlying cause is necessary in order to preserve and restore normal growth potential early in childhood [1, 2]. In gener-al, there are three major categories of HPrl causes in childhood: physiological, pathological and iatrogenic. The aim of this review is to focus on the evalua-tion of HPrl in adolescent and young girls. In addition, we aimed to summarize the current knowledge regard-ing the proper management of such cases.

It is known that our country is located in a geographically dry climate region far from sea level. Today, goiter is developing in our country as a result of a lack of iodine. This leads to complications such as infertility, menstrual cycle disorders, and galactorrhea. The main reason for this is the abnormally high level of prolactin in pubescent girls, the increase in the amount of prolactin, and the decrease in the amount of estrogen hormone disrupt the maturation of follicles.

Material and methods: Subjective observation of girls aged 18 to 25 in our country whose prolactin level is higher than normal and determining the reasons. Inspection object and methods. The causes of hyperprolactinemia were studied as a result of subjective and objective observation among girls aged 18 to 25 years from different regions of our country. As a result, it was determined that 0,9 of the 20 patients had hypothyroidism, and 0,1 had pituitary tumors and various benign tumors.

Results. There are several different conditions that are linked to prolactin over production and secretion. Although rare, pediatric prolactinoma represents one of the most frequent forms of pituitary adenoma. Pituitary adenomas in children and adolescents are benign disorders with an estimated incidence of 0.1/1,000,000 (11). These tumors may be hormone-se-creting (e.g. prolactinoma) or non-hormone-secreting (e.g.incidentalomas). Pediatric prolactinoma predominantly is detected in early puberty. The exact etiology remains enigmatic although in most of the cases they are sporadic forms. Girls

are affected more frequently with microadenomas (<10 mm in diameter) where prolactinomas tend to be smaller and less aggressive compared with boys. Clinical symptoms, prolactin hypersecretion and typical brain magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) findings confirm the diagnosis. Pediatric prolactinoma may also coexist with hormonal deficiencies in thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) and growth hormone (GH) which is more common in macroadenomas(10-40mm)^[6]. From all of these risk factors mentioned above, pharmacological treatments (antiepileptics, antipsychotics) and pituitary adenomas are considered to be the most frequent HPrl causes in childhood and adolescents.^[2,6] Clinical diagnosis and assessment of HPrl in adolescence is determined by the symptoms of the functional syndrome (primary or secondary amenorrhea, galactorrhea) and the presence of any pre-existing medical condition that could lead to HPrl. It is widely accepted that HPrl in the absence of clinical symptoms is not diagnostic^[6]. An adequate physical examination (including gynecological examination) should be conducted, in order to assess patient's mammary glands (galactorrhea), skin (acne, hair growth indicative for PCOS) and any clinical sign which could be linked to a certain medical disorder (10). For the diagnosis of HPrl, blood sample through venipuncture should be obtained without excessive venipuncture stress, in the morning hours (2 hours post-awakening) in order to avoid any false positive HPrl due to circadian acrophase shift ^[1]. Screening through evaluation of prolactin levels is suggested in children and adolescent girls with short stature and/or obesity because they are in a higher risk ^[1] Due to the pulsatile secretion of prolactin, a single measurement of prolactin concentration > 20 ng/ml is not reliable for the diagnosis of HPrl in childhood ^[1] At least two abnormal prolactin values in samples obtained on different days with a pre-test 20-min free interval are suggested to confirm HPrl. In cases where prolactin concentration is extremely high (>100 ng/ml) and or associated with clinical symptoms, a single measurement is adequate ^[1]. As far as the prolactinoma is concerned, prolactin levels >100 ng/ml demonstrates a high predictive and diagnostic value ^[6] A prolactin level higher than 500 ng/ml is diagnostic for macroprolactinoma. In adolescent girls with prolactinoma, serum prolactin levels are 10 times greater in macroadenoma compared to microadenoma. Moderate elevation of prolactin cannot exclude the possibility of tumorous etiology other than various organic or functional causes, and may be due to prolactinoma (1st measurement), incidentaloma or other masses that can compress the

pituitary stalk (6). Particularly, it should also be noted that prolactin level <200 ng/ml with compatible history of medication indicates drug-induced (iatrogenic) HPrI^[5]

The causes of hyperprolactinemia were studied as a result of subjective and objective observation among girls aged 18 to 25 years from different regions of our country. In this case, the general blood analysis of patients, TTE, T4(free), AT-TPO, common vitamin D, prolactin, radiograph of the thyroid gland, MRI of the brain-pituitary gland, and complaints of the patient: weakness, hair loss, drowsiness, menstrual cycle disorders, breasts such as the presence of pain and various discharges were examined. Hypothyroidism caused by iodine deficiency was found to be the main cause of increased prolactin levels in about 18 patients. In the remaining 2 of our patients, it was found that it was caused by the presence of microadenomas in the pituitary gland. And etiologic and symptomatic treatment measures were applied to patients. Also, preventive measures such as increasing the number of sea products in the diet of patients, and doing physical exercises were carried out. Some scientific articles have the following conclusions:

1. It is necessary to determine prolactin in each girl with unexplained amenorrhea irrespective of galactorrhea. 2. In some patients with prolactinoma the basal prolactin levels may be in the normal range, but they are increased in the MTC test. 3. In girls with various disorders of the menstrual cycle it is necessary to determine the level of prolactin with a provocative test.^[7]

Conclusion: As a result of the obtained diagnostic conclusions, it was determined that the main reason for the increase in the amount of prolactin observed in adolescent girls is iodine deficiency. In most of them, it was also found that they do not do enough physical exercises, and lack or lack of vitamins in their diet. The treatment technique should also be carried out according to the reasons.

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